

Under pressure: observational determination of the pressures in HII regions across the Galactic centre and nearby galaxies

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Young (pre-SNe) stellar feedback

High-mass stars are fundamentally important for driving the evolution of galaxies across cosmic time, due to the large amount of energy and momentum – stellar feedback – that they inject into the interstellar medium (ISM) during their relatively short lifetimes. This is crucial, as in the absence of any stellar feedback, the ISM would rapidly cool and form stars at a high efficiency, consuming most of the available gas in the galaxy on a short timescale incompatible with observations (see, e.g., [1, 2, 3, 4] for key open questions relating to massive star formation). Recent simulations and observational evidence suggest that feedback in the early (pre-supernova) stages of high-mass stars plays a critical role in destroying molecular clouds, and hence producing the low star formation efficiencies inferred for giant molecular clouds (GMCs) in the Milky Way and many other nearby galaxies [5]. Moreover, it appears the stellar feedback may be a fundamental regulator in the mass and energy cycles within galactic nuclei; including the Milky Way [6].

Much progress has been made by studying stellar feedback within regions that are observationally accessible in the local Universe, which are characterised by relatively low gas pressures ($P/k \sim 10^{4-5} \text{ K cm}^{-3}$). Studies including a larger dynamical range in external pressures are, however, currently lacking within the literature. These are particularly important towards highly pressured environments, where the ambient gas pressure plays a major role in the molecular cloud life-cycle – setting the initial conditions for star formation, the subsequent star formation efficiency, and the impact of stellar feedback. In addition, such studies have significant implications for high- z star formation, as the ISM pressures observed at the peak of the cosmic star formation history are several orders of magnitude higher than those observed in disc galaxies today. I discuss the fundamental question of how the physics of star formation and feedback vary across environments.

Observationally quantifying stellar feedback

To quantify the relative importance of young (pre-SNe) stellar feedback, we place observational constraints on the main internal feedback mechanisms driving the expansion of a large sample of HII regions. In [4, 7, 8], we consider the following pressure terms thermal gas pressure (P_{therm}), direct (and trapped) radiation pressure (P_{rad}), wind (or shocked gas) pressure (P_{wind}). We compare the total internal pressure, $P_{\text{tot}} = P_{\text{therm}} + P_{\text{rad}} + P_{\text{wind}}$, to the confining pressure of their host environments (P_{de}).

Figure 1: An example of a nearby disc galaxy and the Milky Way Central Molecular Zone (CMZ), which were used to study the effects of stellar feedback, and variations as a function of environment. *Upper panel:* Composite three-colour image towards the nearby disc galaxy NGC 1300, taken using HST observations as part of the PHANGS survey [9] (see also [10, 11]). *Lower panel:* Composite three-colour image of the CMZ, taken using the *Spitzer* and *Herschel* telescopes [2, 4, 12].

Stellar feedback across whole galaxy discs

As presented in [7, 8], we investigate the role of early stellar feedback across the whole disc of 19 nearby ($< 20 \text{ Mpc}$) spiral galaxies on the main sequence of star-forming galaxies (stellar masses in range $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.4 - 11$). To do so, we use the sample of ~ 6000 HII regions identified from the PHANGS-MUSE survey (see Figure 1; [10]). The combination of these optical spectroscopic maps, and the data products provided by PHANGS-ALMA [11] and PHANGS-HST [9], are essential to constrain many fundamental internal (e.g., electron density, temperature, radiation field) and external (e.g., dynamical equilibrium pressure, environment) properties of the HII regions.

We find that for these *unresolved* (10 pc scale) HII regions, the P_{therm} is mildly dominant pressure term. We find that the majority of HII regions are over-pressured,

$P_{\text{tot}}/P_{\text{de}} > 1$, and expanding, yet there is a small sample of compact HII regions with $P_{\text{tot}}/P_{\text{de}} < 1$ ($\sim 1\%$ of the sample). These under-pressured HII regions mostly reside in galaxy centres (galactocentric radii < 1 kpc), or, more specifically, environments of high gas surface density (measured on kpc-scales). Using higher resolution observations from HST to investigating the effect of the environment on these regions represents an interesting avenue of investigation [7].

Zooming in on Centre of the Milky Way

In [4], we investigate the effect of higher ambient density and pressure host environments on the *resolved* physical properties and evolution of stellar feedback. For this, we focus on the inner few hundred parsecs of the Milky Way, the ‘‘Central Molecular Zone’’ (CMZ), which is known to host several HII region complexes – e.g., Sgr B2 and B1 regions (see Figure 1; e.g., [2, 12]).

The CMZ is a particularly interesting extreme environment. The average gas densities, gas temperatures, ambient pressures, turbulent velocity dispersion, interstellar radiation fields and cosmic ray ionisation rate factors of a few to several orders of magnitude larger than observed in typical Milky Way disc and SMC/LMC star-forming systems, making it more similar to starburst and high redshift galaxies at the epoch of peak star formation density at $z \sim 1-3$ [13].

We find that the HII regions are dominated by the direct radiation pressure on only the smallest scales (< 0.01 pc), and at all larger scales they appear to be dominated by the thermal pressure of the ionised gas ($> 0.01-10$ pc). There is evidence for a modest contribution from trapped IR radiation or hot stellar wind gas early in the expansion.

Stellar feedback as a function of environment

Comparing the CMZ HII regions to the extragalactic sample (see Figure 2), and samples taken from the literature, we find that the radius at which HII regions reach pressure balance with their environments is $\sim 2 - 3$ pc in the Galactic Centre, versus > 10 pc in the extragalactic sample. Interestingly, we see that the maximum sizes of HII regions in the Galactic Centre match the radius at which the internal pressure matches the ambient ISM pressure for most environments. This suggests that the smaller HII region within the CMZ are limited by the point of pressure equilibrium with the more highly pressured ambient medium.

Stellar feedback regulated star formation

Given the remarkable similarity between the HII region radii and the radius at which the region pressure drops to the ambient pressure, we suggest a scenario where

Figure 2: Literature compilation of the internal pressures of the HII regions. The total internal pressures as a function of the HII region sizes, ranging from the Milky Way centre from [4] to nearby disc from [8] (see also [14, 15, 16, 17, 18]). The dashed diagonal lines show linear and power of two relations between the pressure and sizes.

star formation can proceed until the gas accretion can be halted, irrespective of the environment. In this case, star formation and feedback self-regulate such that each cloud attains the integrated star formation efficiency required for a blowout, which happens when the developing stellar population can drive the HII region radius to the cloud (or gas disc) scale height.

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